

Issues of Education in the Chronicles of the Khiva Khanate - As an Object of the History of Pedagogy

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Abstract:

In this article, the issues of education and upbringing in the annals of the Khiva khanate - as an object of the history of pedagogy - are considered theoretically and methodologically. Also, the approaches of experts in this regard are analyzed. In place of the conclusion, the author's opinions on the topic are presented.

Keywords: Khanate of Khiva, bell dynasty, oasis of Khorezm, Munis Khorezmi, Ogahi, artistic-literary, historical work, manuscript.

Introduction: As we know from our history, as the captain of the chroniclers of the bell dynasty, Munis Khorazmi occupies a special place in terms of his socio-political views, which greatly influenced the creators of the next generation, and, importantly, in terms of the scale of theoretical and practical significance of his work in education. When studying the history of pedagogy and socio-philosophical thought of the peoples of Central Asia, it is extremely important to study the legacy of Munis in depth and comprehensively. Because the study, research and wide promotion of the creativity of many brilliant allomans who were bred in the Khorezm oasis, which is part of this land, plays a huge role in enriching the spiritual worldview of our people, especially in educating young people, in educating them as individuals with extraordinary maturity and perfection, the humanistic ideas of our great ancestors play an important role. In the end, President Sh.M.Mirziyoyev, in his lectures and speeches, noted that the restoration and popularization of the incredibly valuable spiritual and cultural heritage created by our ancestors for many centuries, which has risen to the level of state policy, is an extremely important task. In particular, it was noted: "Currently, more than 100,000 manuscripts are stored in the book collections of Uzbekistan."

Unfortunately, these rare books have not yet been fully studied, they are waiting for scientists and their readers. In these unique works, you can find answers to a huge number of pressing problems that the modern era puts in the middle. But it is also necessary to openly admit that we have not done enough to become heirs of such a unique heritage, owners of such wealth, to read them in all possible ways - to study, to bring our people closer, first of all, to our growing youth, to the world community." [1.14].

Thematic analysis of the literature:(literature review). The first relation to the personality and work of Muhammad Reza Ogahi can be found in the works of his contemporaries[2.26]. Taking into account that most of the direction of the history of classical literature is the interpretation of the socio-political and educational views of our great predecessors, the analysis of the way their worldviews are expressed, V. Abdullaev [3.127-137], A.Kayumov [4.] studied the poet's work from a literary point of view, V.Zokhidov[5.], G.Karimov, S.Dolimov, etc., in the works of our leading scientists, we find many notes on education and training in the works of Ogakhi. An important source for the analysis of the philosophical world of Mohammad Reza Ogahi is, of course, his historical works. Regarding the historical and scientific significance of these works, V. V. Barthold's "No matter how brief the literary and historical works created by Munis and Ogahi are, according to the description of historical events and the abundance of factual materials presented in them, they surpass all the works that have come down to us about the Kokand and Bukhara khanates" [6.285-286]. Although it is difficult to say exactly what V. V. Bartold meant by "disadvantage", in any case, this opinion of the scientist was born as a result of evaluating the historical works of Muniz and Ogaha from the point of view of European chronicles and approaching them with the requirement of a purely historical work.

In fact, Ogaha's lyrical works are also distinguished by the fact that much attention is paid to education and upbringing. Therefore, the publication of the book "Tawiz ul-Ashikin" can be regarded as a serious shift in science[7.]. The merits of R. Majidi[8.] in the development of computer science should be particularly noted. In the scientific analysis of Ogahi's lyrics, R. Majidi paid special attention to the literary environment of Khorezm and the issues of literary influence in it. S. Dolimov's scientific research [9.221] is of great importance in the development of science at the modern level.

Research Methodology. Despite the fact that the issue of following Alisher Navoi is a very broad topic in the socio-political views of the great representative of the literary environment of Khorezm of the nineteenth century, Muhammad Reza Ogahi, we would like to draw attention to only one side of the views of predecessors and successors. In one place, Firdousul-Iqbal tells the following story: In this place, several soldiers from Khojaly and residents of Karakalpakstan killed the owner of hay without permission. And a political verdict was necessary for the fulfillment of this verb content.He was punished.

Подшоҳимки, жоми адл била,

Хаста мазлумларни айлар шод.

Аҳли бедоднинг сиёсат ила,

Хирмани айшини қилур барбод.

Нукта. Ҳукамо дебдурларким, салтанат ниҳол масобасидадур, сиёсат сув манзиласида. Бас, лозим ва лобудийдур, ул ниҳол решасин бу сув била тоза ва сероб қилмоқ, то бориамну самараи амон ҳосил бўлғай. Қитъа:

Ҳуш ул шаҳриёрики, дониш юзидин,

Адолат мазоминини айлар азбар.

Дами тиг ила салтанат бўстонин,

Сиёсат суйидин қилур тозау тар.

Analysis and results. It seems that the topic, which is apparently a moral concept, is considered at the level of an important socio-political concept, and indeed, the political significance and economic consequences of attention to the issue are revealed by a clear example.

We also see important socio-political theses on the same topic in the work of Alisher Navoi. In particular, Alisher Navoi writes in "Badoeul-vasat" on one of his continents:

Эй Навоий, олам аҳлида тамаъсиз йўқ киши,

Ҳар кишида бу сифат йўқтур, анга бўлгай шараф.

Сен агар тарки тамаъ қилсанг, улуг ишдур буқим,

Олам аҳли барча бўлгай бир тараф, сен бир тараф.

Focusing above on an excerpt from Firdavsu-l-Iqbol, people of the society reflect on the horror of the consequences that the activation of Tama-hissi will bring, that the fight against it will be intense and regular.

Conclusion/Recommendations. That is why, according to the thinker, the water that lifts the sprout of the country and does not allow it to dry up is politics – rigor, regular attention. This does not allow the oppressed to act as they know, to go beyond their limits, being self-sufficient:

Подшоҳимки, жоми адл била,

Хаста мазлумларни айлар шод.

Аҳли бедоднинг сиёсат ила

Хирмани айшини қилур барбод.

Thinkers who have seen firsthand what ugly consequences tobacco has in society, and who have felt how strongly it affects the socio-political, cultural and educational situation, consider the fight against it as one of the criteria of justice:

Хуш ул шахриёрики, дониш юзидин,

Адолат мазоминини айлар азбар.

Дами тиг ила салтанат бў стонин,

Сиёсат суйидин қилур тозау тар.

Reading Ogakhi's historical works, as we have seen, shows that one of the important moments in the formation of Ogakhi's worldview in educational issues, such as socio-political, educational, was the work of Alisher Navoi.

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